

SEARCH FOR NEW ANTISPASMODICS. PART II.

By T. N. GHOSH

Synthesis of a thiazylpyrazolone derivative (II) and the corresponding methylene-bis compound (III) is described.

Following the observation of Notkin and Webster (*Rev. Canadian Biol.*, 1942, 1, 66) that amidopyrine, which is a pyrazolone derivative, possesses antispasmodic activity, the synthesis of some pyrazolone derivatives containing tertiary bases has been described in part I (Pathak and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1949, 28, 371). Investigation is in progress to see if these compounds have any broncho-dilator effect.

Heilbron and his co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 419) have synthesised a number of pyridylquinoline and thiazylquinoline derivatives, some of which have been found to possess pronounced antispasmodic action with the promise of useful additions to the range of drugs suitable for treating asthmatic and other conditions. In view of these observations, it has been considered desirable to synthesise thiazylpyrazolone derivatives as possible antispasmodics.

The hydrochloride of 1-phenyl-3-amino-5-pyrazolone (Weissberger and Porter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2133) has now been allowed to react with potassium thiocyanate to yield the corresponding thiocarbamide derivative (I). When (I) is reacted with $\alpha\beta$ -dichlorodiethyl ether, the thiazylpyrazolone derivative (II) is obtained.

(I)

(II)

A survey of the chemistry of efficient antispasmodics shows that they are, in general, salts of tertiary bases. In order to enhance the antispasmodic activity, it has been considered worth while to introduce tertiary bases into the above compound (II). Compounds other than ketones, but containing an active methyl or methylene group, may sometimes be induced to respond to Mannich reaction (cf. Kermack and Muir, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3089; Pathak and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). As the compound (II) contains a reactive methylene group, it was substituted for the ketone in the usual Mannich reaction which, however, when attempted with piperidine hydrochloride and formaldehyde, did not yield the expected tertiary base but furnished the methylene-bis compound (III). In this respect the above pyrazolone derivative (II) behaves differently from 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone or its 4-acetyl derivative, both of which respond to Mannich reaction (Pathak and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

(III)

In this connection, reference is made to the formation of methylene-bis-antipyrene, when antipyrene is employed for the usual Mannich reaction (cf. Lieberman and Wagner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, 14, 1008).

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Phenyl-3-thiocarbamido-5-pyrazolone (I).—1-Phenyl-3-amino-5-pyrazolone was prepared according to the method of Conrad and Zart (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 2282), as modified by Armstrong (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2134, footnote). The alcohol used should be absolute, otherwise the presence of traces of moisture lowers the yield considerably.

The above amino compound (8.8 g.) was dissolved in just the requisite quantity of dilute hydrochloric acid and to the clear solution a concentrated aqueous solution of potassium thiocyanate (6.2 g.) was added, when a heavy oil was obtained. The mixture was then heated on the wire-gauge for about 20 minutes and then allowed to cool. The solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol in light yellow rectangular plates (7.5 g.), shrinking at 190° and decomposing at 198-99°. It is readily soluble in cold dilute alkali and precipitated by excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. It is desulphurised when an alcoholic solution is boiled with yellow oxide of mercury. It was dried at 95°-100° in *vacuo*. (Found: N, 23.72. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_4S$ requires N, 23.93 per cent).

1-Phenyl-3-(thiazyl-2'-)amino-5-pyrazolone (II).—To a hot alcoholic solution of the compound (I, 7.5 g.) *o*,*i*-dichlorodiethyl ether (5 g.) was gradually added, and the solution was heated on the water-bath under reflux for 2 hours, when it turned red. The solution was diluted sufficiently with water and the mixture was heated on the water-bath for one hour more. The pasty mass, thus obtained, was purified by solution in cold dilute alkali and precipitation by dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol in reddish brown needles (5.2 g.), m.p. 220-21° (decomp.). It was dried in *vacuo* at 110°-115°. (Found: N, 21.38. $C_{12}H_{10}ON_4S$ requires N, 21.70 per cent). The compound is not desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury, proving the presence of sulphur in the ring and the formation of thiazole derivative.

Methylene-bis-[1-phenyl-3-(thiazyl-2'-)amino-5-pyrazolone] (III).—A mixture of the above compound (II, 7.7 g.), piperidine (3.8 g.), hydrochloric acid (8.1 c.c., 20% w/v) and formaldehyde (3.4 c.c., 40%) in alcohol (75 c.c.) was heated under reflux on the water-bath for 8 hours. Next day alcohol was distilled under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with water, filtered and found to be not a hydrochloride. It was purified by treating successively with cold caustic soda solution (1%) and with dilute hydrochloric acid, in both of which it was practically insoluble. It was finally crystallised from alcohol in brownish needles, m.p. 259-60°. (Found: N, 20.86. $C_{20}H_{18}O_2N_8S_2$ requires N, 21.21 per cent).

The above reaction was carried out in absence of hydrochloric acid (compare Lieberman and Wagner, *loc. cit.*), first at room temperature for 12 hours and afterwards by heating on the water-bath under reflux for 6 hours. Under these conditions also, only the above compound (III) could be isolated.